

EDUCATIONAL STAND FOR RESEARCHING THE OPERATION OF AUTOMATION ELEMENTS AND DEVICES**Zamikhovskiy L.,***Doctor of Science, professor***Zamikhovska O.,***Ph.D. in technology, associate professor***Ivanyuk N.,***Ph.D. in technology, associate professor***Mohylin V.,***assistant***Pavlyk V.***Ph.D. in technology, associate professor**Ivano-Frankivsk National**Technical University of Oil and Gas***ABSTRACT**

The article considers a training stand that includes a number of sensors, normalizing converters and hardware and software, mainly from the Ukrainian manufacturer - the company "Mikrol", and reflects the behavior of the control object in educational conditions and without restrictions on its structure. This allows students to simulate the structure of any automated control system, work with it as with real equipment, apply real physical signals via measurement channels to its inputs and gain skills in setting up regulators, configuring and programming automation equipment and PLCs, etc.

Keywords: training stand, hardware and software, sensors, regulators, control object, software.

Problem statement. Today, in the training of specialists in automation, computer-integrated technologies and robotics, who will implement the concept of "Industry 4.0" in practice, the decisive role is played by the combination of theoretical knowledge obtained by them with practical skills. The latter requires gaining experience in working with various monitoring, control or management systems, in particular distributed (WEB-oriented) on real objects and processes, which forms a deep understanding of the essence of automatic control in students and helps in mastering the profession.

However, it is not always possible to deal with real objects or processes, which requires new approaches to solving this problem in the training of specialists. One of the directions for its solution is the creation of various educational stands based on information and communication tools, which combine elements (sensors, measuring modules, etc.) and devices (hardware and software, etc.) of automation and special application software, which are connected to models or models of research objects.

Analysis of recent achievements and publications. A significant number of educational and laboratory complexes have been developed for the educational process, which include separate stands and methodological instructions for their use. Thus, in [1] a laboratory stand is provided for studying the principles of controlling a Schneider Electric electric drive, which is integrated into an automation system via a Modbus network, which allows students to gain skills in configuring a frequency converter for operation in an industrial Modbus network and controlling it using a PLC. In [2] the implementation of a composite laboratory workshop based on the hardware and software tools Multisim-LabVIEW-ELVIS II from National Instruments is considered, a characteristic feature of which is the com-

bination of virtual, computational and full-scale experiments. A description of the laboratory stand and examples of its use when conducting simulation (machine) modeling on the Multisim software platform and a full-scale experiment on the ELVIS II workstation and LabVIEW virtual devices are given. The main directions of designing the hardware part of a computerized educational tool for practical study of the industrial nanocontroller "Relpol" (Poland), which is intended for automation of simple technical or technological processes, are considered in [3]. The process of building the structure of the simulator stand and simulation models of the behavior of industrial automation objects using the example of a vending machine for drinks are considered in [4]. A description of individual subsystems and the process of developing the hardware and software complex of the control object simulator are given.

The concept of most of the considered training stands is a computer measuring tool, additionally equipped with special application software and various measuring modules, which allows you to automate operations for collecting, processing and presenting measuring information, has a convenient interface and is used mainly for training students of technical specialties [5-7].

Identification of an unsolved problem. The considered training stands are intended for studying hardware and software of specific companies, their software, simulation of individual objects and do not allow modeling the structure of ACS TP for various purposes.

Purpose of the article. Creation of a modern multifunctional stand, the use of which will allow you to improve the learning process by developing a cycle of laboratory work on the disciplines "Fundamentals of industrial automation systems", "Industrial automation systems", "Organization and testing of industrial com-

munications of control systems" of the specialty "Automation, computer-integrated technologies and robotics",

Basic material. The presence of modern laboratory stands and educational equipment has always been an indicator of the quality of teaching technical disciplines in higher education institutions. There is practically no doubt that the level of laboratory and technical facilities of an educational institution helps the teaching staff to properly organize the educational process and prepare high-quality specialists who meet the modern demands of employers.

The creation of modern multifunctional training stands equipped with the latest automation elements and devices and operating mock-ups or models of control objects allows students to work with them as with

real objects - to apply signals via physical channels to their inputs, measure signals, adjust regulators, configure, program automation devices and PLCs, etc.

The training stand developed at the Department of Information and Telecommunications Technologies and Systems of the Ivano-Frankivsk National Technical University of Oil and Gas for studying the operation of automation elements and devices (Fig. 1) contains a number of modern sensors of physical quantities complete with appropriate programmers, normalizing signal converters, certified spark gaps, microprocessor regulators and controllers of the domestic manufacturer "Mikrol", cable and wireless communication modules, PLCs with operator-level software.

Fig. 1. General view of the training stand for studying the operation of automation elements and devices

On the basis of the training stand, a cycle of laboratory work was developed on the subjects "Fundamentals of Industrial Automation Systems", "Industrial Automation Systems", "Organization and Testing of Industrial Communications of Control Systems", etc.. An electronic laboratory kit was used,

consisting of high-precision converters of physical quantities, controllers, communication devices and software. The level of sensors on the stand is represented, in particular, by a microprocessor absolute pressure converter from Fisher-Rosemount, type 3051TA2M (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. General view of the absolute pressure transducer 3051TA2M, accuracy class 0.1

Configuration and parameterization of the above-mentioned absolute pressure transducer 3051TA2M is carried out using the HART communicator from Fisher-Rosemount, presented at the stand. The HART communicator (Highway)

The front panel of the controller contains:

- Digital displays,
- Technological signaling indicators of the corresponding channels,
- Controller status indicators,
- Programming keys.

On the rear wall there is a connector for connecting the device's power supply and a connector for connecting terminal block connectors intended for connecting external input and output circuits.

Fig.3. Microprocessor regulator MTR-8

Addressable Remote Transducer) is a manual interface that provides data exchange between any microprocessor devices that support the HART protocol (in-

cluding transducers from other manufacturers, for example, Honeywell). The controller level at the stand is represented by microprocessor complexes from the domestic manufacturer "Mikrol" of the type MTP-8 [8] (Fig. 3), MIK-51 [9] (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Microprocessor controller MIK-51

The MTP-8 microprocessor controller contains configured control loops (PID, three-position, etc.), the functions and operating parameters of which can be changed from the keyboard on the front panel of the device or using the Mic-Configurator software package (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Setting up the MTP-8 regulator in the Mic-Configurator program

MIK-51 is a compact multifunctional microprocessor controller designed for automatic regulation and logical control of technological processes. The controller is programmed using the front panel keys or via the RS-485 interface using special software - the visual editor of FBD programs ALPHA [10]. The programming system is implemented in accordance with the require-

ments of the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) standard IEC 1131-3 and is intended for the development of application software for data acquisition and control of technological processes using programmable controllers. The system uses the Function Block Diagram (FBD - Fig. 6) language as its programming language, which provides the user with a mechanism for object-oriented visual programming.

Fig. 6. Example of programming the MIK-51 controller using FBD functional block diagrams

Communication devices on the training stand are represented, in particular, by the Advantech EKI-1524 terminal server (Fig. 7), which is a four-port serial data transmission gateway from RS-232/422/485 ports to the Ethernet network, with which devices with RS-232/422/485 interfaces can be connected to the Ethernet network (Fig. 8).

Fig. 7. Advantech EKI-1524 terminal server

Fig. 8. Connecting local automation devices to the Ethernet network

The presence of two independent Ethernet 10/100Base-TX ports in the EKI-1524 allows for the simplest redundancy of the communication channel. The EKI-1524 terminal server supports several operating modes: virtual COM port with multiple access, TCP and UDP client/server. With the help of the Advantech EKI-1524, you can organize a direct connection via the Ethernet network for four serial devices, each of which will function without any programming or external control.

The operator-level software is presented on the training stand by the software package "MIC-Register" [10] (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Software package "MIC-Registrator"

The software package "MIK-Registrator" is a system for collecting and archiving information and provides:

1. Collection and archiving of information received from controllers, regulators, and technological indicators of the "Mikrol" enterprise (in the demo version up to 16 measuring channels):

- regulators MIK-51, MIK-12, MIK-2, MIK-21, MIK-22, MIK-25, MTR-8, MTR-44,

- technological indicators ITM-1, ITM-2, ITM-10, ITM-11, ITM-12, ITM-20, ITM-22.

2. Display of technological information (obtained during device interrogation) in the form of graphs, with the appropriate service for selecting and scaling information,

3. Organization of a log of technological and emergency messages.

The obtained data are used for systems: visualization, measurement, registration, analysis, control and management of the technological process and/or equipment, as well as archiving data on the computer's hard drive.

Conclusions.

1. The developed training stand can:

- be used for various purposes depending on the purpose of a specific academic discipline related to the specialty "Automation, computer-integrated technologies and robotics";

- serve as a tool for debugging various automation systems;

- serve as a testing ground for conducting scientific research related to the development of automation systems.

2. Using the training stand will allow students to acquire skills in integrating automation elements and

devices into APCS and SCADA, as well as gain experience in installing and configuring devices and systems.

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